

Simultaneously observing particle and wave behavior of light

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Utilizing methods first theorized by T. Young to test whether light mimicked the behavior of classical waves, we demonstrated interference patterns indicating wave behavior with single photons. Our methods involved measuring the horizontal location of individual photons on the surface of a detector after a light beam passed through a double-slit blocker. The two slits produced an interference pattern which demonstrates the perplexing quantum phenomena of photons interfering with themselves— a fundamental deviation from classical physics.

I. INTRODUCTION

One of the foundational questions within the field of quantum mechanics was whether light behaved with as a classical particle or as a wave. In his famous Double-Slit experiment, Thomas Young sought to prove that light behaves like a classical wave by observing an interference pattern when a light beam passed through two parallel vertical slits[1]. He expected that, if light acted in the same manner a wave, the interference pattern— bands of very bright and very dark measurements caused by the light waves interacting with one another— would appear upon downstream measurements of the slits. However if light was instead made up of very small particles, one very bright spot directly in the center of the measurement area that faded slowly off to the sides would arise where the particles scattered and landed. After performing his Double-Slit experiment, Thomas Young observed an interference pattern, indicating that light has wave-like properties.

FIG. 1. An 1807 drawing by Young illustrating the principles of the double-slit experiment.

Puzzlingly, later experiments were able to detect individual packets of light — photons— which behaved as particles upon detection, but still built up an interference pattern [2]. An object exhibiting properties of both particles and waves had never been observed before, and could not exist in the realm of classical mechanics. This deviation from classical physics is what Feynman referred to as the heart of quantum mechanics in his 1963 lectures. This phenomenon is commonly referred to as wave-particle duality of light, although some find that

FIG. 2. A photo of the interference pattern produced by a laser in a modern two-slit experimental apparatus.

description to be misleading since more advanced understandings of the phenomena deal exclusively with wave functions [3]. Qualitatively, we observe *both* particle and wave qualities in the light downstream of the double slit.

A. Description of Experiment

We utilized the TeachSpin Two-Slit-Apparatus to replicate Young’s Two-Slit experiments to measure individual photons and display an interference pattern. The two-slit apparatus sends a light beam along an enclosed U-channel to a photomultiplier. In between the light source and the detector there are a number of components which allowed for adjustment of the slit locations, and thus several different types of measurement. We calibrated these components to ensure that the light beam was centered against the photomultiplier. The final mounted slit that the light beam encounters is a single slit directly in front of the detector, and is adjusted by means of a micrometer. The detector slit allows only a slim vertical stream of light to reach the photomultiplier. This allowed us to measure the exact location along the surface of the detector where photons were detected. The data output from the photomultiplier is a voltage which could be read by a counter/timer and digital oscilloscope, allowing us to make a count of how many photons reached a given point on the detector.

In order to count as many photons as possible without counting background noise, we adjusted the trigger level on both the counter/timer and oscilloscope so that

they were identical and provided the greatest difference between dark and bright counts upon repeated measurement. Further discussion of our comparison between bright and dark counts is relegated to the data subsection of the results section.

II. RESULTS

A. Taking Data

Our data consists of measurements of the counts read from the photomultiplier over an interval of 10 seconds. Each count was triggered by the arrival of a photon at the detector. The detector then sends a voltage signal as an output from the TeachSpin Apparatus that is then read by a counter/timer. The counter/timer counts the number of times the TeachSpin Apparatus measured the arrival of a photon. Bright counts were measured with the bulb's light on and with the detector's shutter open. To account for the noise that we would measure, Dark counts were also measured. Dark counts were measured with the shutter closed.

B. The Data

FIG. 3. Raw data from slit with $d = 14$ imported directly from the Jupyter notebook.

FIG. 4. Raw data from slit with $d = 18$ imported directly from the Jupyter notebook.

Qualitatively, this data in Figure 3 and Figure 4 absolutely supports the wave-particle understanding of the

behavior of light. Although only one photon reached the detector at a time, we still observed positive and negative interference when the double slit was in place. Note also that the dark counts are well below the total counts, indicating that the majority of the particles we measured were photons. This can be compared to the single slit, Figure 5, which displays no interference pattern.

FIG. 5. Raw data from the single slit imported directly from the Jupyter notebook.

III. DATA ANALYSIS

A. Quantified Uncertainty

We utilized the following relation for uncertainty proposed for experiments involving photon counts:

$$\sigma_{r_s}^2 = \sigma_{r_{s+b}}^2 + \sigma_{r_b}^2$$

Where r is the count rate, s is the source, b is the background, and, of course, σ is uncertainty. We made the following determinations:

$\sigma_{r_b} = 8.161$, which was the standard deviation of the twelve background counts we measured.

$\sigma_{r_{b+s}} = 41.296$, which was the standard deviation of twelve different bright counts we performed at the same micrometer location. We selected a micrometer position of 2.5 with the 14 mm slit since this was a location of maximum sensitivity given the steep slope in the graph at this point, demonstrating a dramatic change in photon counts between this micrometer setting and the next.

From this, we calculated the following:

$$\begin{aligned} \sigma_{r_s} &= \sqrt{\sigma_{r_{s+b}}^2 + \sigma_{r_b}^2} \\ &= \sqrt{8.161^2 + 41.296^2} \\ &= 42.095 \end{aligned} \quad (1)$$

Which we used as error bars on our data. This is significant only when our data neared the dark count values, which is acceptable.

B. Theory

The purpose of this experiment was to test the theory that light behaves with both particle and wave properties. A wave passing through two slits will interfere with itself and produce a pattern of alternating positive and negative interference bands on a detector. Particles passing through two slits will pass through one or the other and produce a peak behind each slit. Therefore, measuring the result of light passing through two slits ought to indicate whether it is a particle or a wave. One of the foundational problems of quantum mechanics is the problem of measurement: by measuring a system, one alters it. Upon measurement of light at very, very low intensities, it is clear that a detector picks up a single point of light— a photon— but that is no proof that light always behaves as a photon particle, since the measurement may have altered its behavior. The demonstration of this is in the single photon double slit experiment we performed. Although only a single photon was in the U-channel at a given time, an interference pattern was produced. This indicates that the light passed through both slits at once, like a wave, but collapsed and hit the detector at exactly one point, like a particle. This is in support of the theory that light demonstrates both wave and particle behaviors.

C. Quantified Analysis

Since the primary purpose of this experiment was to observe a photon interfering with itself, we needed to be reasonably certain that there was only one photon in the U-channel at a time, instead of two photons getting through and interfering with one another. We performed the following analysis, and are extremely confident that our data represents photons interfering with themselves.

The probability of a photon being in the U-channel is given by:

$$P(n, \mu) = \frac{(\bar{r} \cdot \Delta t)^n}{n!} \cdot e^{-\bar{r}\Delta t}$$

Where:

- n is the number of events (number of photons reaching the detector)
- Δt is the amount of time it takes a photon to travel from emission to detector, from the following calculation using L , the length of the U-channel, and c , the speed of light: $= \frac{L}{c} = 1.05m \cdot \frac{1s}{2.9979 \cdot 10^8 m} = 3.5 \cdot 10^{-9}s$
- \bar{r} is the rate of emissions of photons. We estimated this value by taking the maximum emission with a single wide slit in place of the double slits. This ensured that no light was blocked from the detector, and we got a fair estimate. This maximum was $\frac{580 \text{ photons}}{10s} = 58p/s$

Using this information, observe the following:

The probability of there being no photons in the U-channel in a given Δt is:

$$\begin{aligned} P(0) &= e^{-\bar{r}\Delta t} \\ &= e^{-58 \cdot 3.5 \cdot 10^{-9}} \\ &= 0.9999 \end{aligned} \quad (2)$$

The probability of there being one photon in the U-channel in a given Δt is:

$$\begin{aligned} P(1) &= (\bar{r}\Delta t) \cdot P(0) \\ &= (0.58 \cdot 3.5 \cdot 10^{-9}) \cdot 0.9999 \\ &= 2.02 \cdot 10^{-9} \end{aligned} \quad (3)$$

Similarly, the probability of there being two photons in the U-channel in a given Δt is:

$$\begin{aligned} P(2) &= \frac{1}{2}(\bar{r}\Delta t) \cdot P(1) \\ &= \frac{1}{2}(0.58 \cdot 3.5 \cdot 10^{-9}) * 2.02 \cdot 10^{-9} \\ &= 2.06 \cdot 10^{-18} \end{aligned} \quad (4)$$

Since the probability of there being two photons in the channel at the same time is so much lower (by a factor of 10^{-9}) than the probability of there being one photon in the channel, we can be extremely confident that we are measuring photon self-interference.

We wish to compare our data to the following model:

$$I = I_0 \sin^2(\alpha) \cdot \cos^2(\beta)$$

Where:

$$\begin{aligned} \sin c(\alpha) &= \frac{\sin(\alpha)}{\alpha} \\ \beta &= \frac{\pi a}{\lambda \sin(\theta)} \end{aligned}$$

The angle θ is the angle (measured at the double slit in radians) between the midpoint of the U-channel and the point at which the measurement of a photon occurred.

Although both data sets clearly display an interference pattern, note that in order to achieve an acceptable fit of the data to the model, we introduced a slight offset in the angle θ of approximately -0.0003 in the $d = 14$, and -0.0012 in the $d = 18$ plots, Figures 7 and 8, respectively.

FIG. 6. Curve fit for single slit data imported directly from the Jupyter notebook.

FIG. 8. Curve fit for double slit with $d = 18$ imported directly from the Jupyter notebook.

FIG. 7. Curve fit for double slit with $d = 14$ imported directly from the Jupyter notebook.

D. Analysis of Curve Fit

To verify that the data supports the model beyond the visual fit, we utilized a χ^2 test:

$$\chi^2 = \sum \frac{\frac{\text{residuals}^2}{\text{uncertainty}}}{\text{points} - \text{d.o.f.}}$$

The residuals were calculated by subtracting a given data point from the value of the model at that point. The subtraction of the degrees of freedom (d.o.f.) from the number of data points is standard practice in a χ^2 test.

The results of the test are listed in Table I. These very low reduced χ^2 values are a signifier that our data is well described by the model including identifiable systematic

errors, but our estimation of error on the measurements is too high and requires further investigation. Note also that this calculation of χ^2 is only based on data in the range $-0.008 \leq \theta \leq 0.008$, which is exceptionally narrow.

Slit Separation	χ^2 Value
14	0.028
18	0.035
Single	0.011

TABLE I. Results of χ^2 Calculations

IV. CONCLUSION

The data satisfactorily demonstrates photon self-interference, by aligning with the model of classical interference when only one photon reached the photomultiplier at a time. Ideally, more data would be taken in the form of both repeated data sets and finer modulation of the micrometer in the two-slit apparatus to produce more data points in each set, but the existing data is more than sufficient.

[1] T. Young, (1802).

[2] H. Rauch, *Physics World* , 15 (2002).

[3] H. Nikolic, *Found Phys* **37**, 1563 (2007).